

Accumulation of lead, cadmium, nickel and copper in hair of people living near heavy traffic area

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Abstract : Accumulation of Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu in the hair of 462 males living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area in various parts of Rajasthan (India) was studied. Out of 462, 231 lived near heavy traffic area and remaining lived near less traffic area. Head hair samples from nape were obtained from subject under study alongwith filling up of a questionnaire recommended by World Health Organisation. Hair samples were washed, digested to get a colourless and clear solution and then analysed by AAS for Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu concentration. Subjects were grouped into four age groups of 21 to 30 years, 31 to 40 years, 41 to 50 years, 51 to 60 years. While significant concentration of Pb was found in all age groups of people living near heavy traffic area as compared to people living near less traffic area, that of Ni was not significant. Difference in Cd and Cu concentration of hair of people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area was not found significant in all age groups.

Keywords : Hair, heavy traffic area, less traffic area, lead, cadmium, nickel, copper, Atomic Absorption Spectrometry.

Introduction

The change in the way of living of man, activities performed by him to make life more comfortable has redistributed many elements in the environment. Increase in road traffic using petrol, diesel and other fuels dump a large amount of pollutants in the environment. Man himself as a part of environment is greatly affected by the environmental pollution¹. These elements enter in the body through inhalation, ingestion, absorption through exposed parts of the body and injection². In chemistry, elements are classified on the basis of their physical and chemical properties into metals, non-metals and metalloids. On the basis of requirement and importance in body, elements are classified into bulk elements (C, H, O, N, S), trace elements (Fe, Ni, Cu, Mg, Na, K etc.) and toxic elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As etc.)³. As the concentration of any particular element increases in body and exceeds the limit, it starts interfering with the metabolism and biochemical effects of other elements⁴. Gradually these elements accumulate in different parts of body shows adverse health effects. Exposure to elements, if leads to accumulation of elements, may cause various ill effects on health like neurological problems, respiratory problems, cancer and infertility etc.⁵⁻¹⁰.

Biomonitoring of hair can be done to determine the concentration of different components like nicotine, opiates, trace and toxic metals¹¹⁻¹³. Hair is used as biopsy material in different fields of science such as Medicine, Forensic, Environmental and Archaeology¹⁴. Hair is the best non-invasive biological tissue, which is used in biomonitoring of elements¹⁵. It is one of the fastest growing tissues of the body, so it requires adequate supply of blood, nutrient, minerals etc. to grow, so it can keep a complete record of elements present in the body¹⁴. The analysis of concentration of elements in hair can be done by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS), Proton-Induced X-Ray Emission Spectrometer (PIXE), Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA), Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (IC-PMS), X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (XRF)¹⁶.

In the present study concentration of two toxic metals lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) and two trace metals nickel (Ni) and copper (Cu) was determined in hair of people living near Heavy Traffic Areas (HTA) and Less Traffic Areas (LTA) in Rajasthan (India). Total 462 subjects between 21 to 60 years of age were included in the study, of which 231 lived near HTA and remaining 231 lived near LTA. Hair samples were washed and digested and analysed

using AAS. It was hypothesized that people living near HTA have higher concentration of Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu in their hair as compared to people living near LTA. It was also goal of this study to determine the relation, if any, between trace (Cu and Ni) and toxic metal (Pb and Cd) concentration in hair as all the metals under this study are heavy metals. The main aim of this study was to identify the population at risk to metals in environment due to increasing traffic.

Results and discussion

Mean and standard deviation of metals under study in hair samples have been calculated and presented with respect to their age group and residential area. As summarized in Table 1 mean lead concentration in hair of people living near HTA was significantly higher than living near LTA. Highest mean value of 26.757 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (± 6.668) of lead in hair was found in people of age group 51–60 years living near HTA, where as lowest mean value of 3.352 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (± 1.626) of lead in hair was found in people of age group 21–30 years living near LTA. Thus it is clear from Table 1 that subject living near HTA are more

exposed to lead and this exposure leads to accumulation of lead in hair.

Cadmium level in hair of people living near HTA and LTA is summarized in Table 2. Highest mean value 0.454 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (± 0.510) of cadmium in hair was found in people of age group 51–60 years living near HTA, in contrast to lowest mean value 0.095 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (± 0.047) of cadmium in those of 21–30 years age living near LTA. Significant cadmium levels were found in subjects of age group 21–30 years living near HTA as compared to people living near LTA. When comparison was made among other age groups it was revealed that though Cd level was not significantly different between people living near HTA and LTA, but subjects in all age groups residing near HTA have higher concentration of Cd than those near LTA. High exposure to Cd is clearly depicted in Table 2.

Table 3 records the nickel levels in hair of people living near heavy and less traffic area. The results obtained show that the metal concentration in hair is a function of period of exposure³. High levels of Ni in higher age groups of people residing near heavy traffic areas

Table 1. Lead level in hair of people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area

Age group (N =)	Near heavy traffic		Near less traffic	
	Range ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Range ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
21–30 (N = 59)	2.50–50.00	25.017 ^a (± 14.091)	1.53–5.53	3.352 (± 1.626)
31–40 (N = 62)	5.71–51.42	26.744 ^a (± 15.434)	2.85–220.26	21.358 (± 53.111)
41–50 (N = 58)	0.70–46.10	21.160 ^a (± 10.206)	7.10–15.13	13.468 (± 2.521)
51–60 (N = 52)	16.91–37.31	26.757 ^a (± 6.668)	16.71–17.90	17.470 (± 0.660)

^aSignificant difference between people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area by $P < 0.05$.

Table 2. Cadmium level in hair of people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area

Age group (N =)	Near heavy traffic		Near less traffic	
	Range ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Range ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
21–30 (N = 59)	0.04–0.51	0.130 ^a (± 0.121)	0.03–0.15	0.095 (± 0.047)
31–40 (N = 62)	0.03–0.34	0.293 (± 0.276)	0.03–0.85	0.230 (± 0.249)
41–50 (N = 58)	0.03–0.68	0.285 (± 0.236)	0.05–0.96	0.268 (± 0.309)
51–60 (N = 52)	0.08–2.08	0.454 (± 0.510)	0.07–1.30	0.433 (± 0.314)

^aSignificant difference between people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area by $P < 0.05$.

Table 3. Nickel level in hair of people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area

Age group	Near heavy traffic		Near less traffic	
	Range (µg/g)	Mean (µg/g)	Range (µg/g)	Mean (µg/g)
21-30 (N = 59)	0.13-2.23	1.377 (±0.673)	0.13-2.50	1.385 (±0.994)
31-40 (N = 62)	1.80-23.10	9.220 (±8.785)	2.10-23.10	9.373 (±8.617)
41-50 (N = 58)	3.00-27.50	6.136 (±6.897)	3.00-21.20	8.947 (±8.621)
51-60 (N = 52)	4.92-29.00	12.266 (±9.301)	5.18-21.50	10.926 (±9.168)

show that older people are more prone to metal pollution, although the levels were not significant in this case. The relatively lower levels of nickel in hair of people living near HTA than those near LTA might be due to replacement of Ni from its biological sites or any other biological influence due to other metals.

Copper levels in hair of people living near HTA and LTA are summarized in Table 4. Highest mean value 17.290 µg/g (±11.301) of copper in hair was found in people of age group 41-50 living near HTA, where as lowest mean value 5.900 µg/g (±3.43) of copper in hair was found in people of age group 21-30 living near LTA. Significant copper level was found in people of age group 21-30 and 41-50 years living near HTA as compared to people living near LTA. There was a high variation in concentration of copper in different age group in same area, as is clear from Table 4. This change might be due to influence of any other metal at binding sites of copper.

Table 1 to Table 4 clearly reveal that subjects living near HTA are exposed to toxic metals like lead and cadmium released from exhaust of vehicles and these toxic metals gets accumulated in the hair. This accumulation was of different levels in people of different age groups. Cu and Ni level in hair was not found higher in people of all age groups, which indicate that people living near HTA are not exposed to these metals. On the other hand, a high degree of variation was found in level of these metal in hair of people living near HTA.

From Table 1 to Table 4 the relationship between level of toxic metals and essential metals in hair of subjects living near HTA can be ascertained. Hair copper level is related with hair lead level, a finding that is also supported by reported works¹⁷⁻¹⁹. An observation of data of Table 1 to Table 4 between age group and mean value of concentration of metals in hair, leads to show that with increase in concentration of lead in hair the concentration

Table 4. Copper level in hair of people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area

Age group	Near heavy traffic		Near less traffic	
	Range (µg/g)	Mean (µg/g)	Range (µg/g)	Mean (µg/g)
21-30 (N = 59)	1.23-16.13	9.140 ^a (±6.011)	1.50-11.64	5.900 (±3.43)
31-40 (N = 62)	0.58-19.09	10.067 (±6.549)	0.58-29.00	10.786 (±3.568)
41-50 (N = 58)	4.30-47.00	17.290 ^a (±11.301)	8.07-17.70	11.893 (±3.859)
51-60 (N = 52)	9.38-19.81	16.312 (±3.818)	13.90-18.56	16.920 (±2.618)

^aSignificant difference between people living near heavy traffic area and less traffic area by $P < 0.05$.

of copper decreases³. A decrease in lead concentration of hair leads to higher concentration of copper in hair. This result supports the fact that toxic metals interfere with the biological functions and biochemical reactions of essential metals. The same trend was also identified between level of copper and nickel in hair i.e. an increase in nickel and decrease in copper concentration in hair. This supports our earlier work that trace metals interfere with the biological functions of other trace metals¹⁷. A very interesting relation was found between nickel concentration in hair and lead concentration in hair, the nickel level in hair varies similarly as the lead level in hair. Metal level in hair is also dependent on age, as in this study concentration of all the metals under study was found least in people of age group of 21–30 years and highest level of metals was found in people older age group (41–50 and 51–60). This result is in agreement with that reported by Barbosa *et al.* according to which teeth and bones accumulate metals in them and thereafter releases metal in blood with span of time²⁰. From these studies, it is found that population living near HTA is exposed to toxic metals as compared to population living near LTA and they accumulate these toxic metals in their body. These toxic metals interfere with the biochemical reactions of essential metals, which may lead to various health hazards.

Experimental

Selection of site for HTA and LTA where workers of locomotive workshop lived was done in Rajasthan (India). 462 male subjects of 21 to 60 years of age were selected; out of these 462 subjects 231 lived near HTA and remaining 231 lived near LTA. Head hair samples from nape region were taken using a stainless steel scissor, which was rinsed with ethanol. Approximately 2 g of samples were taken with 1 cm distance from scalp and stored in airtight polythene. While sampling, other information of subject like age, sex, occupation was also obtained from a questionnaire. All subjects were grouped into four categories of age, which are 21 to 30 years, 31 to 40 years, 41 to 50 years and 51 to 60 years.

Hair samples were washed with non-ionic detergent (Triton X-100), acetone and deionised water and kept for drying at 110 °C in oven for one hour. Wash and dried samples were then digested using nitric acid and perchloric acid in 6 : 1 ratio, until a colourless clear solution is

obtained. All chemicals used in the present study were of AR grade. The acid is now evaporated and residue is then dissolved in 0.1 N nitric acid^{21–23}. The quantitative analysis of Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu was performed with an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) Perkin-Elmer Model-5000 using air acetylene flame. Cathode lamps were used which was set at 283, 229, 232 and 325 nm separately for Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu respectively. The data obtained from AAS in µg/ml were converted into µg/g using following formula.

$$\mu\text{g/g} = \frac{\mu\text{g/ml (experimental value)} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{weight of sample in g}}$$

where,

$$\text{dilution factor} = \frac{\text{ml of final volume}}{\text{ml of 0.1 N nitric acid taken for dilution}}$$

Suitable statistical methods were applied to interpret the data.

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Note

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